

Creating coherent cycling networks: A spatial network science perspective

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Abstract

Provision of a coherent cycling network is essential to facilitate cycling uptake. In recent years, several data-driven methods for optimizing the design of cycling networks and for prioritizing infrastructure interventions have been published. Still, many aspects regarding the integration of systemic importance and bikeability of road segments and, related to this, the effects of spatial method parameters on emerging spatial patterns have not been widely studied.

Addressing identified gaps in current approaches, we propose a method that integrates systemic segment importance derived from spatial betweenness centrality with a continuous bikeability index for segment prioritization. Based on this method, we introduce a procedure for assessing spatial effects in data-driven methods for designing coherent cycling networks. Application of this procedure in diverse urban and rural areas showed feasibility of the proposed prioritization method and revealed a fundamental impact of distance parameters on emerging spatial patterns. While changes in maximum routing distance (local betweenness) highlight structures relevant for mobility at different scales, node subsampling may induce significant bias especially for short routing distances. Computation of segment importance based on bikeable paths instead of shortest paths shows the intended spatial shift towards corridors of high-quality cycling infrastructure where available.

From the results, we conclude that spatial parameters together with the specific integration of bikeability with systemic importance have substantial influence on the outcome of optimization methods for designing coherent cycling networks. Therefore, we call for nuanced approaches, making use of multiple scenario views or explorative, interactive tools in planning processes.

Keywords

Spatial network analysis, local betweenness centrality, planning support, cycling infrastructure, prioritization of infrastructure interventions, gap detection, scale

Supplementary Materials

Results, Software (source code) and Data: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13336596>

1. Introduction

Transport networks are commonly digitally represented as spatial graphs. This facilitates network analyses for multiple purposes, from route optimization to traffic simulation or planning applications (Loidl et al., 2016). Various methods for gap detection and prioritization of segments for infrastructure improvement have been proposed in recent years, aiming at creation of coherent bicycle networks. In their review focusing on connectivity of cycling networks, Schön et al. (2024) see great value in such methods for efficient planning support and demand for further research targeting their optimization. Within this work we focus on the geospatial perspective and assess the impact of scale-related method parameters on results. For this we formulate a network assessment approach that uses a synthesis of methods with evolutionary improvements applied.

We address the following research questions:

How and to what extent do distance parameters in routing (cutoffs and linear decay) and spatial node subsampling influence the geospatial patterns that emerge from optimization algorithms for cycling network coherence? Linked to this, how can commonly utilized approaches for prioritizing road segments in cycling network optimization be improved?

For the research presented in this paper, we pose the hypotheses, 1) that the aforementioned spatial parameters impact results of data-driven network planning approaches by introducing scale-related side effects which widely remain unconsidered, and 2) that many prioritization approaches utilize a simplified, opportunistic combination of cycling flow data or network centrality on the one side and bikeability on the other.

Consequently, we assess existing literature on data-driven optimization methods for coherent cycling networks with a focus on spatial aspects and routing parameters. Furthermore, we investigate prevalent gaps regarding segment-level bikeability in the computation of priority scores. Based on these findings, we propose a method that integrates detailed segment-level bikeability and a spatially normalized centrality indicator resulting in a priority score for network optimization. For this enhanced method we test the sensitivity for distance parameters in routing (cutoffs, decay functions) and node subsampling. To further promote open and reproducible science, we make all code and data available online.

1.1. Literature and Background

In this subsection we provide an overview of previous works that target data-driven optimization for coherent cycling networks, structured according to the key methods applied. It serves providing context for this work as well as addressing part of our research question and hypothesis regarding spatial aspects.

1.1.1. Assessing the graph structure and modelling demand or flow

Continuity of cycling networks is critical for establishing cycling as safe and convenient mode of transport. Consequently, methods for prioritizing interventions rely on network science approaches to assess connectivity and network structure.

In all methods we reviewed, routing or graph traversal algorithms are applied implicitly or explicitly during some stage of processing. However, their use differs in terms of purpose, scale, input network, and parametrization. A minimal use is to detect connected components of coherent bicycle infrastructure as in Natera Orozco et al. (2020). The majority of approaches utilize routing to assign cycling demand or flow metrics to individual road segments.

Some works base their cyclist flow or demand assignment on revealed origin-destination (OD) flow data from cell phone networks (e.g. Olmos et al., 2020; X. Zhao & Guo, 2024), authoritative (commuter) data (e.g. Mahfouz et al., 2023; Zuo & Wei, 2019), or micromobility sharing data (e.g. Folco et al., 2023; Steinacker et al., 2022). The use of revealed OD data ranges from merely defining cutoff distances for bikeable routes to directly assigning revealed flow to OD pairs, typically filtered by bikeable distance. Other approaches such as by Vybornova et al. (2023) and Szell et al. (2022) utilize betweenness centrality to approximate flow.

A major difference between existing approaches is whether routing is applied directly to the road network or to an artificial network of straight lines between OD pairs. The latter is primarily used by network growth algorithms to rank OD relations by importance (e.g. Folco et al., 2023; Szell et al., 2022). Out of the investigated approaches which use the road network for routing, only Vybornova et al. (2023) considers routes between all pairs of nodes in the network. The other methods rely on a subsampled set of OD nodes. This node subset is mostly defined based on the data used for flow estimation, and consequently represents centroids of census districts or administrative zones, locations of micromobility sharing stations, or cell phone antennas. Few cases define nodes to approximate a regular grid (e.g. Folco et al., 2023; Szell et al., 2022). Where explicitly mentioned, distances between the nodes range from 300 meters to more than 1500 meters. In many cases neither node distances nor average cell sizes are stated. However, from contextual information and maps shown, the typical node distances are expected to be scattered around the upper bounds of this range.

A further aspect to consider is whether routes are generated to favor bicycle-friendly infrastructure or merely optimize for shortest path distance or travel time. Olmos et al., (2020) and X. Zhao & Guo (2024) utilize external services or software packages for generating bicycle-friendly routes. However, the exact logic and parameters for path generation are not presented. The works by Mahfouz et al. (2023), Moran et al. (2018), Steinacker et al. (2022) and Q. Zhao & Manaugh (2023) generate bikeable routes following a scalarizing approach which assigns a weighted (perceived) distance as cost for shortest path generation. The weight assigned to each segment is meant to represent perceived suitability and safety or is inversely defined as penalty factor. Despite advanced methods for quantifying segment-scale bikeability being available, the presented works utilize simplified metrics as proxy.

Zuo & Wie (2019) follow a different approach that only considers the lowest cycling suitability of road segments per path for assessing bicycle accessibility of origins and destinations. Caggiani et al. (2019) select the path with highest coverage of bike lanes out of a set of alternative shortest paths for use in their accessibility metric.

Although stated as possible future extension, routes are optimized towards shortest travel time in Paulsen & Rich (2023) and do not regard segment-level suitability at all. Vybornova et al. (2023) also rely on shortest (distance) path computation but compensate for potentially existing parallel segments with protected bicycle infrastructure in gap detection.

Maximum path distance is regarded in most approaches, sometimes implicitly. Commonly, either a single fixed distance cutoff is set to limit the maximum distance of routes to be considered for cycling (e.g. Vybornova et al., 2023), or a decay function is applied (e.g. X. Zhao & Guo, 2024). In other cases, distance is implicitly covered through direct use of demand data for routing (e.g. Steinacker et al., 2022).

1.1.2. Assessing segment-scale bikeability

If the methods are targeted towards prioritizing segments for infrastructure upgrading within real-world road networks, the present suitability of infrastructure should be considered in the assessment. Some methods, however, are targeted towards generic network design strategies for creating cycling networks from scratch. Several of these methods do not assess present segment-scale bikeability at all. Examples are the approaches by Paulsen & Rich (2023) and X. Zhao & Guo (2024).

Interestingly, despite utilizing slightly more detailed bikeability metrics for routing, some methods fall back to very simplistic classification of segment suitability for prioritization of road segments. The majority of approaches reduce the segment-level suitability indicator to a binary variable. These mostly regard the presence of protected cycling infrastructure as sole criterion. Folco et al. (2023) additionally include mixed infrastructure types such as cyclestreets in their binary classification. Zhao & Manaugh (2023) utilize a bikeability classification consisting of three levels of suitability which is based on local network data. The inverted network growth approach by Steinacker et al. (2022) proxies disutility of road segments through OSM road category.

1.1.3. Prioritization strategy

Prioritization of road segments for infrastructure upgrading mainly follows two approaches in the given context: either directly prioritizing unsuitable segments by flow or following an iterative network growth method.

The most simplistic and straight-forward approach applies binary classification to segment suitability (bikeable vs. unbikeable segments), and prioritizes unbikeable segments based on highest flow. Examples for this category are Mahfouz et al. (2023) and Moran et al. (2018).

Other concepts are based on iteratively growing (or shrinking) the bikeable network. This can take place on abstracted level such as between network components (e.g. Natera Orozco et al., 2020; Q. Zhao & Manaugh, 2023), sampled OD relations (e.g. Folco et al., 2023; Szell et al., 2022), or for the individual road segments (e.g. Steinacker et al., 2022).

Despite following a similar overarching objective, methods differ in what they optimize for. Following their approach of minimizing disutility of iteratively removed ideal infrastructure, Steinacker et al. (2022) favor direct (shortest path) connections along main roads. Methods such as by Mahfouz et al. (2023) better integrate existing high-quality bicycle infrastructure and aim for filling the most relevant gaps in terms of flow on bikeable routes.

Multi-objective optimization is utilized by Zuo & Wie (2019) to target prioritization of individual variants from a set of pre-defined bike plans. They regard metrics of accessibility as well as implementation costs of bikeways, and induced delay for motorized traffic. However, assessment relies on spatially coarse census districts as spatial units and route bikeability is determined by the least bikeable segment only.

Some methods explicitly address equitable access, such as Caggiani et al. (2019) and Q. Zhao & Manaugh (2023), as well as Mahfouz et al. (2023) within their egalitarian approach.

While several growth-based methods are designed for developing new cycling networks from scratch, others make use of existing infrastructure and aim for filling prevalent gaps in partly developed cycling networks. The methods by Lowry et al. (2016), Zhao & Manaugh (2023) and Zuo & Wei (2019) require planned cycling infrastructure as an input and do not detect remaining gaps or segments for improvement.

1.1.4. Scale and spatial aspects

Despite addressing an inherently spatial phenomenon, spatial characteristics, and especially scale are not regarded in most of the literature reviewed. The work by Vybornova et al. (2023) is a notable exception, where distance-restricted (local) betweenness centrality is applied and its role to mitigate center-bias of centrality metrics is briefly discussed. The authors argue for the use of a 2.5 km cutoff distance to represent “sub-city scale flows” (Vybornova et al., 2023, p. 8), thus explicitly addressing scale. Folco et al. (2023) within their supplementary S3 discuss the influence of distance between seed points on their method for a specific study area and found it to be rather robust – without regarding spatial patterns. The work by Lovelace et al. (2020) is another example, where different ways to define the spatial area of interest are illustrated and briefly discussed. Still, the potential (spatial) effects introduced through choice of distance cutoffs, node subsampling, and choice of the area of interest widely remain hidden in the literature reviewed. Although known, the edge effects of standard betweenness centrality (Gil, 2017) are widely omitted in these methods.

Regarding scale, the betweenness-related concept of *choice in space syntax* (Hillier & Iida, 2005) is partially applied to local subsets defined through circular node buffers of different size. However, this typically aims at assessing an area for different modes of transport. Furthermore, many space syntax applications neglect inherent spatial characteristics such as distance, albeit known to be important (Turner, 2007).

While not regarding cycling networks, the work by Yamaoka et al. (2021) provides first insights regarding potential effects of distance-cutoffs in betweenness centrality on emerging spatial patterns. They relate to the distance-restricted betweenness centrality metric as *local betweenness centrality* and propose a visualization technique for assessing this metric for a range of distances. However, their assessment relies on shortest paths, does not account for node density, and does not quantify differences from a network perspective.

1.2. Summary of the Research Gap

Table 1 provides a summary of the reviewed literature regarding the key elements discussed in the previous section.

	Routing approach				Prioritization		Required input
	Routing OD	Network type	Distance restriction	Routing <i>SP/BP: shortest / bikeable path</i>	Segment bikeability <i>x: binary</i>	Prioritization strategy	
Lowry et al. (2016)	O: Area (district), D: point (POI)	Road	3.22 km (2 miles)	BP (LTS-based)	-	Projects ranked by length-weighted average centrality of segments	Residential + business pop., cycling infrastr. projects
Moran et al. (2018)	Area (district centroid)	Road	(limited by bicycle netw. components)	BP (4 suitability classes)	x	LTS 3 segments ranked by highest flow	Demand data
Caggiani et al. (2019)	Area (district centroid)	Road	x	k-shortest; BP post-selection	x	Optimize equitable access (planned infrastructure, budget)	Planned cycling infrastructure
Zuo & Wei (2019)	Area (district centroid)	Road	Distribution (GPS survey)	k-shortest; BP post-selection	LTS classes	Multi-criteria; consider max. LTS per route	Planned cycling infrastructure, GPS travel survey data
Lovelace et al. (2020)	Area (district centroid) / POI	Road	Implicit: flow data	SP with elevation	3 classes (based on speed limit)	Flow threshold, filter on suitability of road for pop-up infrastructure	Demand data, road width
Natera Orozco et al. (2020)	-	Road	-	-	x	Minimize length of connections added between network components	-
Olmos et al. (2020)	Point (cell phone stations)	Road	Distribution (GPS data)	Shortest time (using OSRM)	x	Determine highest flow threshold which maintains netw. connectivity	Demand data (OD), GPS trajectories
Steinacker et al. (2022)	Point (bike sharing stations)	Road	Implicit: flow data	BP	4 classes (based on road cat.)	Inverted network growth, priority on shortest paths	Flow data (OD)
Szell et al. (2022)	Regular grid (> 1500 m) / POI	Triangulation network / (road)	-	SP	-	Network growth (different strategies – e.g. betweenness)	-
Folco et al. (2023)	Regular grid (300 m)	Triangulation network / (road)	Implicit: flow data	SP / weighted dist. (accidents, flow)	x	Network growth (based on centrality metric of triangulation network)	Flow data (OD), accident data
Mahfouz et al. (2023)	Area (district centroid)	Road	Implicit: flow model	BP	x	Non-bikeable segments ranked by highest flow	Flow data (OD)
Paulsen & Rich (2023)	Area (district centroid)	Road		Shortest time	-	Various cost-benefit oriented optimization strategies	
Vybornova et al. (2023)	All nodes	Road	2.5 km	SP, BP post-selection (parallel edges)	x	Centrality-based gap detection, benefit assessment, clustering	-
Q. Zhao & Manaugh (2023)	Network components / area (district centroid)	Road	5 km (in one scenario)	BP (6 classes)	3 classes	Different strategies; based on trip count	Existing + planned bike network, commuting data (OD), POIs
X. Zhao & Guo (2024)	Point (cell phone stations)	(Raster)	(flow / distance decay)	(cost surface, regard feasibility)	-	Route classification based on estimated potential	Flow data (OD)

Table 1: Summary of the reviewed literature regarding key methodological aspects.

From the literature reviewed in [section 1.1](#) we identified the following shortcomings, which underline the relevance of the research presented in this paper:

- Current methods for prioritizing road segments for infrastructure upgrading fall short at adequately addressing inherent spatial aspects such as the scale of analysis or the scale of the phenomena to assess.
- The potential impacts of distance distributions or cutoff values applied in the routing stage are not regarded explicitly.
- Routing as methodological core is almost exclusively applied for a spatially coarse subsample of OD nodes without adequately considering and quantifying potential side effects.
- Spatial edge effects and approaches for their mitigation widely remain unaddressed.
- Segment-level bikeability is presently approximated through highly simplified metrics which lack evaluation and transparency regarding their definition.
- If regarded at all, segment-level bikeability is not consistently applied across all method stages – i.e. a different metric is used for determining routing cost (bikeable paths) than for segment prioritization.

Consequently, the consolidated objectives of this paper are:

- Assess the impact of spatial method parameters on centrality-based metrics, specifically regarding both the effects of route distance cutoff and decay variants as well as the impact of spatial node subsampling.
- Advance existing cycling network assessment methods to
 - use spatial input parameters that make the scale of emerging mobility patterns explicit
 - more realistically capture segment-based bikeability with its nuances beyond binary classification
 - consistently apply the same bikeability metric across all stages of the method
 - be applicable independent of (potentially non-existing) flow data
 - provide a clearly defined strategy to mitigate spatial edge effects

2. Methods

We propose a method that integrates an established continuous bikeability score of road segments with determining their systemic importance in the network for computing segment priority scores. This forms the basis for data-driven network design. To address the spatial aspects outlined in the previous section, we present a test procedure which systematically applies the proposed prioritization method for several combinations of spatial parameters. This twofold methodological approach is reflected in the structure of this section. First, we introduce the method for prioritizing infrastructure upgrades. Second, we outline the approach for assessing the impact of node subsampling and routing distance parameters (cutoffs and linear decay) on results.

2.1. Prioritization method

We introduce an integrated approach for prioritizing road segments that addresses prevailing limitations of existing methods. For this, we define three subsequent steps which are presented in detail in the following subsections:

1. Assessing segment-level bikeability
2. Determining systemic importance of road segments
3. Computing priority scores from segment bikeability and importance

2.1.1. Assessing bikeability of road segments

For assessing the suitability of road segments for cycling, we utilize the segment-based bikeability index by Werner, van der Meer, et al. (2024). It relies on open data and is available as part of the open source software implementation *NetAScore* (Werner, Wendel, et al., 2024a). This bikeability metric extends the level of detail compared to previously applied simplified proxies and was shown to be suitable for generic bikeability assessment (Werner, van der Meer, et al., 2024). By default, it considers six indicators: type of bicycle infrastructure, designated bicycle route, road category, speed limit, pavement type, and gradient. Furthermore, it can easily be customized to represent specific requirements of local contexts and individual target groups. The chosen bikeability index further allows shifting from binary classification of cycling networks to a more differentiated perspective, as it assigns continuous numeric bikeability scores to each road segment, ranging from 0 (unsuitable) to 1 (very suitable). Thus, it fills a main gap concerning bikeability assessment we identified in [section 1](#). Furthermore, we consistently apply the same bikeability assessment throughout the workflow: It is utilized both in the routing stage as well as for segment prioritization.

2.1.2. Assessing systemic segment importance

Szell et al. (2022) argue for utilizing a generic network science approach focused on network topology for determining segment importance, which is independent of (potentially limited) flow data. We follow this line of argument. Instead of utilizing revealed flow data that represents past mobility patterns, this allows for a generic, forward-directed perspective that aims at enabling mobility for everyone and any purpose. The approach is based on the general concept of *betweenness centrality* (Freeman, 1977) which is similarly applied as *choice* in space syntax (Hillier & Iida, 2005). It facilitates assessment with low data requirements.

The foundation of the improved method we propose is the spatial betweenness centrality metric described by Werner & Loidl (2023a). It compensates for spatial bias introduced by variation in node density through weighting paths according to spatial coverage of origin and destination nodes. It further captures contributions by all nodes of a network (subset) instead of utilizing node subsampling which may introduce substantial bias. We further extend this approach by limiting the spatial weights to built-up and leisure areas. This prevents agricultural land, forest, and other plot types which cover large areas but have low importance as

destination from impacting centrality. Details can be inferred from the software implementation and its accompanying documentation, accessible via the supplementary materials.

Furthermore, in order to represent realistic bicycle mobility patterns, we compute spatial edge betweenness centrality using *bikeable routes* instead of shortest paths. Bikeable routes aim at minimizing travelled distance while maximizing segment-level bikeability. To reduce complexity of this multi-criteria routing problem, we utilize a scalarizing approach which combines real-world segment length with segment bikeability into a perceived distance metric per network edge. This allows for applying standard shortest path routing algorithms and is in line with past research (e.g. Grigore et al., 2019; Moran et al., 2018; Steinacker et al., 2022). In order to avoid zero-length segments, we assign a minimum perceived distance equal to the real-world segment length l in case of highest suitability (bikeability=1.0). Segment length is further re-scaled negatively proportional to its bikeability, up to a maximum perceived distance of $(d + 1) * l$ (with routing factor $d = 4$ by default) in case of lowest bikeability (bikeability=0.0). This approach ensures that routes make use of suitable bicycle infrastructure if available within reasonable detour from shortest paths.

Another important extension to the spatial betweenness centrality method is the introduction of distance cutoff (and optionally distance decay). While this has been applied to standard betweenness in previous studies (e.g. [Vybornova et al., 2023](#); [Yamaoka et al., 2021](#)), the combination of perceived distance as routing cost with a spatial route distance cutoff requires adaptation to the routing algorithm. Details can be found in the accompanying software implementation. Limiting the maximum route length allows investigating mobility patterns of specific scales and enables restricting bicycle routes to common trip lengths for utilitarian cycling (Łukawska, 2024). Furthermore, distance restriction enables mitigating spatial edge effects of standard betweenness centrality (Gil, 2017; Vybornova et al., 2023; Yamaoka et al., 2021). Through spatially buffering the core area of interest by the maximum routing distance, one can make sure that all routes that might involve any of the core area road segments are computed. Thus, zones potentially affected by edge effects are well defined and can be accounted for.

Regarding access restrictions, we filter the network to exclude segments which are neither accessible to cyclists nor to pedestrians (such as motorways). However, in order to increase tolerance towards data quality issues and to maintain network connectivity, we still include segments only accessible to pedestrians. These are assigned an additional penalty in the routing stage, to only be utilized in case of no suitable alternatives being present within reasonable detour.

Implementation of the extended spatial edge betweenness centrality method is based on the code by Werner & Loidl (2023b), which extended the SIBC algorithm of Wu et al. (2022) built on top of the NetworkX centrality implementation by Hagberg et al. (2008). Besides the methodological extensions outlined in this section, we added further algorithmic optimization based on spatial properties. For length-restricted centrality, the network is pre-filtered to destination nodes within the given maximum Euclidean distance from each source node to improve computational efficiency. Furthermore, we implemented a method for simplifying the network which aims at reducing impact on segment importance results. Details are provided in the code repository documentation. We verified the suitability of this approach following the

method outlined in section 2.2, comparing centrality results with those computed on the original input network. Results are presented in [section 3.1](#).

2.1.3. Prioritizing road segments

In the last step, segment bikeability and systemic segment importance are combined to determine the priority score. This approach is in line with the general logic of previous prioritization strategies (e.g. [Mahfouz et al., 2023](#); [Moran et al., 2018](#); [Zhao & Manaugh, 2023](#)). As segment importance considers available bicycle infrastructures in routing where feasible, remaining segments of low bikeability but high systemic importance are of utmost relevance for infrastructure upgrading. Thus, the prioritization approach should rank combinations of high systemic importance and poor bikeability highest, while segments of low systemic importance in combination with good bikeability should rank lowest. Furthermore, segments with zero importance or perfect bikeability should be assigned zero priority. In contrast to methods that utilize binary classification of bikeability (i.e. “the bicycle network”), here, two continuous numeric inputs need to be combined. The mathematical function to apply in order to join both values into a single numeric priority score can be a multiplication in the most simplistic case.

We propose the following variants for deriving the combined priority score p from bikeability b , centrality (segment importance) c , and an optional bikeability threshold t :

- $p_0 = (1 - b) * c$
- $p_1 = \frac{t-b}{t} * c$ for $b < t$ and $p_1 = 0$ for $b \geq t$ (equals p_0 for $t = 1$)
- $p_2 = (1 - \sqrt{\frac{1}{t} * b}) * c$ for $b < t$ and $p_2 = 0$ for $b \geq t$
- $p_3 = \left(\frac{t-b}{t}\right)^2 * c$ for $b < t$ and $p_3 = 0$ for $b \geq t$

While p_0 represents the most simplistic approach, it leads to ranking many high-bikeability segments (e.g. bikeability > 0.9) as high priority if segments have high systemic importance. Therefore, p_1 introduces a threshold value t which allows for excluding a range of high-bikeability values. In our examples we use $t = 0.8$ to exclude the upper 20% of the bikeability score range from prioritization. The variants p_2 and p_3 additionally introduce non-linear weighting of bikeability values to emphasize low-bikeability segments. Function p_3 in contrast to p_2 creates a smooth transition at t , while maintaining a closer to linear mapping for low bikeability values. Because of these characteristics we utilize p_3 as preferred function for computing priority scores.

[Figure 1](#) visualizes the characteristics of functions p_1 , p_2 and p_3 for deriving the priority score. All functions meet the defined criteria regarding input value extrema as outlined in the introduction to this section. This approach maintains compatibility with methods that utilize binary classification of bikeability, as bikeable segments can then be assigned a numeric value of 1 and unbikeable segments can be assigned a value of 0. For convenience, min-max-normalized centrality values may be used per area of interest. However, if using the original spatially normalized betweenness centrality metric, priority score results remain comparable between different areas of interest (for the same routing distance cutoff setting).

Fig. 1: Comparison of priority score functions for $c = 1$ and $t = 0.8$.

2.2. Method for assessing spatial effects

We apply the method outlined in [section 2.1](#) to several real-world road networks in order to assess the effects of maximum routing distance, linear distance decay, and node subsampling by distance on segment importance results. The assessment method comprises the following steps:

- Compute bikeability and segment importance following the method outlined in [section 2.1](#), using pre-defined value sets for spatial parameters
- Generate maps for geo-visual comparison of results
- Compute key metrics for quantitative comparison of results

For assessing the influence of routing distance, we defined the following set of distance cutoff values: 2 km, 4 km, and 7 km. Additionally, we regard the following linear distance decay variants: 2-4 km, 4-7 km, and 2-7 km. For linear decay each route's contribution to centrality is multiplied by a factor which linearly decreases from 1 to 0 within the given distance range.

In order to cover the range of commonly applied O-D node distances (see [section 1.1](#)), we use the following distances for grid-based node subsampling: 300 m, 600 m, 900 m, 1200 m, and 1500 m. Thus, results can indicate the potential bias introduced through node subsampling in commonly applied methods.

As the prioritization method attributes high influence to segments with high systemic importance, we focus on assessing effects for these high-importance segments. For this paper, we define high-centrality segments (HC) as all segments with an importance greater than 20% of maximum importance.

For quantitative comparison of importance results we rely on intuitively interpretable metrics which are computed per comparison pair. These encompass the share of HC segments changed, the delta of relative importance, and mean overall change in importance.

3. Results

In the first part of the results section, we focus on assessing the feasibility of the prioritization method outlined in [section 2.1](#) using several real-world examples. The second part builds on

these results and focuses on systematic assessment of scale and spatial aspects, following the approach described in [section 2.2](#).

3.1. Feasibility of the prioritization method

We computed bikeability with NetAScore V1.1.1 (Werner, Wendel, et al., 2024b) using the default bikeability profile for six exemplary areas in Austria. The selected areas represent a wide variety of characteristics, ranging from dense urban areas to rural, sparsely populated alpine valleys. [Figure 2](#) provides an overview map. The areas have dimensions of 37.5 to 56 km in width and height, with the edge effect-free core ranging from 23.5 to 42 km. Each core extent covers an area of approximately 700 to 1400 km². The core areas are defined through a 7 km inset buffer of the respective full extent, covering the maximum routing distance used in our analyses.

Fig. 2: Overview of the selected test areas.

In [Figure 3](#) we present priority score results for all six areas of interest, as well as the respective bikeability and importance layers. From the presented maps the local differences in built-up density, bikeability, and consequently importance as well as priority score results are apparent. While computation time increases with spatial density of the network, the method was successfully applied to all test cases. The share of segments that received a priority score (p_3 to 0.8) of min. 20 % of the respective maximum priority score ranges from 0.1 % for ZS to 1.8 % for ZW, with max. 0.3 % for ZS, Wien, NO and Graz, and 0.7 % for IB.

From the histograms in [Figure 4](#) we can observe the characteristic of priority score variant p_3 to prioritize low-bikeability segments in comparison to p_1 and p_2 , shown for the example cases Wien and ZS. Similar patterns are present for the remaining test cases. Furthermore, the total number of segments that receive high priority scores is reduced with p_3 . This effect can be clearly observed from the maps in [Appendix A.1](#) which visualize results for the different priority score variants.

Fig. 3: Method applied to six example cases (importance and priority for 4 km cutoff distance).

Fig. 4: Histogram of high PS values (≥ 20 % of max. PS) per bikeability class by PS variant for Wien (left) and ZS (right) cases (for 4 km cutoff distance using bikeable paths)

We further assessed the impact of our network simplification approach for all six areas of interest for spatial betweenness centrality using bikeable paths with 2 km and 4 km distance cutoff. Network simplification led to a mean change in high centrality (HC) classified segments of 3.7 % across all areas of interest, ranging from 1.3 % to 6.8 %. Introduced differences were smaller for the 4 km variants compared to 2 km cutoff distance. The mean absolute normalized delta for HC segments ranged from 0.003 to 0.009 across test areas, with a mean of 0.006 (respectively 0.3 to 0.9 % of maximum centrality). Input networks consisted of approx. 64K (ZW) to 244K (Wien) nodes and 151K to 658K edges. The network simplification approach reduced the number of nodes by 55 % on average (43 % to 64 %) and the number of edges by 45 % on average (32 % to 56 %). Result plots illustrating the differences are included in [Appendix B](#).

We provide additional results in [Appendix C](#) that illustrate the specifics of different centrality metrics when used to determine segment importance. The most prominent change is introduced through applying a distance cutoff to standard edge betweenness centrality, which removes the otherwise inherent spatial phenomenon of high centrality clustering towards the spatial center of the area of interest. Furthermore, bikeability-based routing (BP) shows the tendency to attract centrality to fewer segments (of higher bikeability), resulting in a more sparse pattern of high centrality segments compared to shortest path routing (SP). The effects of spatial weighting compared to standard betweenness centrality were already assessed by Werner & Loidl (2023a).

Plots, maps, and result data for all AOIs are available online in the supplementary materials at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13336596>.

3.2. Assessing scale and spatial effects

For all statistical results presented in this section, only the core areas are regarded to exclude the impact of edge effects. Results are generated using the outlined method for segment importance (computing spatial betweenness centrality for bikeable paths with distance cutoff).

3.2.1. Distance cutoff in routing (length-restricted betweenness)

The importance variants computed with 2, 4, and 7 km maximum routing distance shown in Figure 5 for the example of Vienna visually highlight the differences in emerging spatial patterns. While the 2 km variant shows higher density of high-importance (HC) segments throughout all built-up areas, higher cutoff values result in more sparse high-importance corridors. Furthermore, the higher distances reduce the relative importance of road segments within built-up areas outside of the dense Vienna city area. Although there exists some overlap regarding priority score results for the different cutoff-scenarios, priority values get shifted according to the underlying importance layer.

Fig. 5: Importance and priority score results for different routing cutoff distances (Vienna example).

With Figures 6 and 7 we provide additional importance layer examples for a dense built-up area with its more rural periphery (Graz, Figure 6) and a rural area with several small municipalities (ZW, Figure 7). Here, we also show results for the distance decay variants outlined in section 2.2. Both 7 km distance decay variants (4-7 km and 2-7 km) appear very similar to each other as well as to the non-decay variant with 7 km cutoff. Likewise, the 2-4 km decay variant resembles the 4 km cutoff result.

The rural case shown in Figure 7 illustrates the effect of higher distance cutoff values leading to the emergence of higher segment importance on connections between municipalities. This partly results in cohesive high-importance clusters which link the local within-municipality clusters visible for the 2 km cutoff case.

Fig. 6: Importance results for all routing cutoff distances and decay settings (Graz example).

Fig. 7: Importance results for all routing cutoff distances and decay settings (ZW example).

Similar patterns as from visual interpretation of the previously shown maps are observable from Figure 8. While high-centrality segments have relatively high overlap between e.g. 4-7 km decay and 7 km cutoff variants or 2-4 km decay and 4 km cutoff results, most HC segments differ between the 7 km and 2 km cutoff variants (approx. 70%). In general, decay variants appear to be more similar to the cutoff variants covered by the decay range (especially towards

the upper end) than distinct cutoff variants are to each other. Overall, the share of changed HC segments ranges from approx. 10 % to almost 80 %

Fig. 8: Share of changed HC segments by distance decay or cutoff variant ordered by mean value

3.2.2. Grid-based node subsampling

The maps presented in [Figure 9](#) show the difference in min-max normalized centrality introduced by node subsampling for the Vienna case. To enable comparison between the different variants, we use a fixed color scale ranging from -20% of maximum centrality to +20% of maximum centrality. However, in many cases values exceed this range, as visible in the adjacent scatter plots. We can observe from the results, that higher sampling distance is associated with an increased deviation of centrality values from to the non-sampled reference case. This effect is strongest for the 2 km routing distance cutoff and becomes less impactful for the 7 km cutoff variants. Still, many segments deviate by 10-20% of maximum centrality in these cases, starting from 600 m subsampling distance. Regarding spatial location of the introduced changes one can observe a partly regular pattern which appears to resemble the grid used for subsampling. However, induced changes can also be noted beyond these regular patterns for most variants. Several examples can be found where routes are shifted from one road segment to another parallel segment in proximity, e.g. shifting high centrality from one side of a river or block to the opposite side.

Results show high similarity across all test sites (additional examples can be found in [Appendix D](#)). We provide all results for each test area, including centrality maps and plots for the omitted sampling distances of 900 m and 1200 m, and the 4 km routing distance cutoff in the supplementary materials online.

Fig. 9: Min-max normalized difference in spatial centrality (BP) introduced by node subsampling (by sample distance): Example of the Vienna case

On a more aggregated level, results for spatial centrality variants across all AOIs presented in [Figures 10 and 11](#) support the previous observations with a focus on high-centrality segments. While in extreme cases 90 % of HC segments changed, the mean share of changed segments ranges from approx. 17 % for 300 m subsampling to approx. 73 % in the case of 1500 m subsampling distance as shown in [Figure 10](#). When regarding the mean share of changed HC segments by routing distance cutoff, shorter cutoff distance variants are more affected than the 7 km distance. Still, for the 7 km case, the mean share of changed segments ranges from

12 % (300 m subsampling) to 62 % (1500 m subsampling). Similar patterns are observable in Figure 11 regarding the mean absolute normalized delta by subsampling distance.

Fig. 10: Share of changed HC segments by subsampling distance

Fig. 11: Mean absolute normalized delta by subsampling distance

4. Discussion

Within this section, we discuss the results presented in section 3, regard their implications for prioritization methods, outline limitations, and provide an outlook towards future research.

4.1. Prioritization method

The results outlined in section 3.1 proof general applicability of the proposed method to prioritize road segments. We have shown the feasibility to run the reproducible workflow for various areas of interest that span dense urban environments (e.g. Wien) as well as sparsely populated rural areas (e.g. ZW and ZS). Especially priority score variant p_3 showed the desired focus on segments of low bikeability but high systemic importance. Thus, the method is capable of effectively reducing the potential solution space to a manageable number of road segments which can be further assessed by planning experts. The method optimizes for effective and efficient provision of coherent cycling infrastructure along road segments. The routing approach makes use of well-suited bicycle infrastructure where possible within reasonable detour and the prioritization approach consequently highlights relevant gaps of low bikeability that cannot be bypassed.

The prioritization method appears to be best suited for networks with partially developed bicycle infrastructure, as segments with higher bikeability attract routes and thereby locally concentrate importance to fewer segments. This effect is visible from comparison of shortest path (SP) to bikeable path (BP) results. When applied to a network with non-existing bicycle infrastructure, results will highlight a higher share of segments which are part of all shortest paths (as for results of spatial centrality computed using shortest paths). The method could then be applied in an iterative workflow, where in each step a subset of highly prioritized infrastructure is (hypothetically) upgraded to incorporate such “bundling” effects throughout the network development process.

As of the current method definition, expert assessment is required to detect potential corridors that could serve several relations through “bundling” high-priority segments which are in spatial proximity to each other. However, in any case we encourage the use of an interactive, exploratory approach to assess real-world road networks. This allows users to set different filters (e.g. regarding accepted levels of bikeability) and prevents oversimplification through hiding complexity.

The proposed prioritization method does not apply node subsampling by default in order to prevent unintended side effects. If desired for specific purposes, flow-based weighting can be achieved with this prioritization approach through substituting spatial node weights with a pre-computed OD flow matrix in centrality computation. Additional weighting options are outlined in the code documentation accessible via the supplementary materials.

We further showed that the applied network simplification method has comparably low effect on centrality results, and thus appears suitable for the given context.

4.2. Spatial parameters and their effect on emerging geospatial patterns

Results clearly underline the importance of explicitly regarding spatial method parameters and of finding appropriate settings that suit each specific purpose. In the following subsections we detail on the findings regarding routing distance as well as node subsampling.

4.2.1. Distance cutoff and decay in routing

Results for a diverse set of real-world road networks revealed substantial impact of routing distance constraints on the centrality-based segment importance metric. This supports first findings by [Yamaoka et al. \(2021\)](#) which were generated in a generic shortest-path routing context. Additionally, Linear distance decay showed minor influence compared to non-decay variants of the same maximum distance (e.g. 2-7 km decay vs. 7 km non-decay). Across all test cases, the cutoff distance applied to routing had high impact on emerging spatial patterns of centrality results.

While intuitive from the definition of centrality metrics, the resulting patterns of high-centrality segments highlight different structures depending on the routing distance cutoff specified. Short cutoff distance (in our examples 2 km) highlights network structures on a local neighborhood level, with comparably high density across built-up areas of various size.

Medium distance (4 km) reduces the importance of local, peripheral segments and emphasizes the main structures which serve connectivity between local structures. This effect continues for the shift from 4 km to 7 km maximum routing distance, further reducing the importance of local structures and highlighting the segments that foster connectivity on a larger scale.

Following these findings, we can conclude that distance cutoff in routing (or local betweenness threshold radius) allows to explicitly control the scale of geospatial patterns to address. Regarding segment importance (and in consequence priorities) for different levels of scale may be of great benefit for planning and decision making. Therefore, we propose to conduct analyses of segment importance and prioritization of road segments for a set of scale levels suitable to the application case. For the present application in cycling mobility, following exemplary scale levels and associated human-interpretable labels may be used for orientation:

- 2 km: neighborhood scale
- 4 km: local scale
- 7 km: local interlinking scale

Results can then be assessed and discussed in context of the respective scale and can easily be combined into a single information layer if desired, e.g. following the visualization approach by [Yamaoka et al. \(2021\)](#).

Furthermore, integrating bikeable routes into betweenness centrality computation as well as compensating for node density using spatial betweenness centrality are important conceptual additions that can have substantial effect on the emerging spatial patterns.

Another important aspect that was previously addressed by [Vybornova et al. \(2023\)](#) and by [Yamaoka et al. \(2021\)](#) is the ability of distance-restricted betweenness centrality to mitigate spatial network edge effects (see [Gil, 2017](#)).

With the proposed method and implementation supplemental to this paper, we enable to integrate two different distance metrics in routing. This facilitates computing bikeable routes which consider perceived distance as cost value, while applying a cutoff on spatial network distance of each route. Besides enabling the outlined approach to investigate the effect of spatial parameters, this approach also mitigates the potential bias of contradictory routes outlined in the context of angular distance metrics by [Cooper \(2015\)](#).

As of our findings, mixing of scales which occurs when regarding one single result with (implicit) distance decay may lead to results which are highly influenced by the longest routes considered. Certainly, results are less intuitive to interpret regarding the scale of patterns compared to explicitly defining different scales of assessment for an analysis.

The linear distance decay variants assessed in this work only showed minor effects compared to the non-decay variants with same cutoff distance. However, this may be different for non-linear decay functions.

In contrast to the findings of [Yamaoka et al. \(2021\)](#), where higher distance cutoffs led to high centrality along main roads, our results show higher centrality along main cycling corridors (if available). This is an expected effect of the bikeable path routing applied and indicates suitability of the proposed method for use in the context of planning support for coherent cycling networks.

Furthermore, we observed higher distance cutoffs to enable connectivity between neighboring municipalities in the rural cases, thus attributing higher centrality to road segments that serve

connectivity between more dense built-up areas. While this appears intuitive, depending on the purpose of assessment, the upper routing cutoff distance applied (here 7 km) may need to be extended to be suitable for assessing main cycling corridors on regional scale.

4.2.2. Node subsampling

Across the diverse set of real-world road networks assessed, node subsampling showed considerable impact on centrality results. The effect increased with higher grid size used for node subsampling as well as with shorter routing cutoff distances.

Induced changes were not limited to low-centrality segments, but substantially affected high-centrality segments. Even the lowest subsampling distance we applied (300 m) induced a change in segments classified as high-centrality of approx. 40 % on average.

From visually interpreting the induced spatial patterns we can assume that several effects overlay each other. First, node sampling locations off the core (HC) routes may induce higher than expected centrality for short sections connecting to the core routes through their accumulated O/D weight. Second, weight aggregation towards subsampled nodes may lead to concentrating all respective paths on a single route, while original nodes in close proximity may have been accessible via different (shortest) paths. This may lead to more large-scale effects, e.g. shifting centrality to parallel routes such as from one side of a river or block to the opposite side.

It might be possible to partly compensate some of the aforementioned effects through introducing a more advanced approach to node subsampling – e.g. based on local node centrality. However, such approaches need to be validated, and the remaining bias should be well known before application in planning support. We consider this an important direction for future research.

Overall, the choice of a node subsampling distance needs to be aligned with the scale of assessment, respectively the routing distances to regard. Systematically assessing this relationship for various types of real-world road networks is another promising future research direction.

Our findings highlight the importance to clearly assess the implications that the choice of OD locations may have for a specific study. While the use of points of interest (POIs) as OD locations such as bike sharing stations in Steinacker et al. (2022) can allow well-targeted prioritization towards better connecting these POIs, results may not be applicable to prioritization for the general cycling population due to the spatial bias introduced. Furthermore, spatially coarse OD locations based on census districts or cell phone antennas such as in Lovelace et al. (2020), Olmos et al. (2020) or Szell et al. (2022) can cause substantial spatial bias at scales relevant to cycling mobility. Consequently, their potential impact should be quantified and ideally mitigated before methods are applied in planning support.

5. Conclusion

Within this work we assessed the impact of spatial parameters on methods for planning support in the context of cycling mobility. As part of the assessment workflow, we introduced a method for prioritizing road segments for infrastructure improvement which adds several evolutionary improvements.

From the results obtained for six areas of interest with diverse spatial characteristics we can conclude that both maximum routing distance as well as node subsampling distance have substantial impact on centrality-related metrics. Thus, these parameters should be well defined prior to application in planning support methods.

We argue that it is preferable to explicitly regard different scales in network assessments, which can be defined as a set of routing cutoff distances. Such an approach may ease interpretation and communication of results, being explicit about phenomena of different scale. Additionally, the precise definition of maximum routing distance facilitates the mitigation of spatial edge effects.

Results show that the commonly utilized simplification approach of node subsampling needs to be applied cautiously, as sampling distance needs to be suitable for the respective scale of assessment. Noticeable impact already occurred for a subsampling distance of 300 m, although the effect was less prominent for long routing cutoff distance such as 7 km. If subsampling is applied, remaining side effects should be quantified and stated transparently.

Future research may further optimize approaches for node subsampling that focus on reducing the impact on centrality metrics.

The prioritization method we applied in this research was shown to be applicable for a set of test areas with very different characteristics, ranging from dense urban to rural alpine areas. It consistently applies a fine-grained, validated bikeability metric both in routing and for segment prioritization. Furthermore, it relies on a spatially weighted local betweenness centrality metric to mitigate side-effects of variations in node density, enables explicit regard of scale, and allows for clear definition and mitigation of spatial edge effects. The proposed method does not require node subsampling which was shown to have high potential for bias. Thus, it directly contributes to the advancement of planning support methods. All data and code are openly available to support reproducibility and to ease transfer and further discussion.

Future research may build on this foundation and assess the relations between structure and spatial embedment of real-world road networks, routing distance cutoff, and resulting spatial centrality patterns. If systematic correlations are found, such findings may be of high relevance to the design of network planning support methods.

References

- Caggiani, L., Camporeale, R., Binetti, M., & Ottomanelli, M. (2019). An urban bikeway network design model for inclusive and equitable transport policies. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 37, 59–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2018.12.166>
- Cooper, C. H. V. (2015). Spatial localization of closeness and betweenness measures: A self-contradictory but useful form of network analysis. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 29(8), 1293–1309. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2015.1018834>
- Folco, P., Gauvin, L., Tizzoni, M., & Szell, M. (2023). Data-driven micromobility network planning for demand and safety. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 50(8), 2087–2102. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23998083221135611>
- Freeman, L. C. (1977). A Set of Measures of Centrality Based on Betweenness. *Sociometry*, 40(1), 35–41. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3033543>
- Gil, J. (2017). Street network analysis “edge effects”: Examining the sensitivity of centrality measures to boundary conditions. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 44(5), 819–836. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265813516650678>
- Grigore, E., Garrick, N., Fuhrer, R., & Axhausen, Ing. K. W. (2019). Bikeability in Basel. *Transportation Research Record*, 0361198119839982. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0361198119839982>
- Hagberg, A. A., Schult, D. A., & Swart, P. J. (2008). Exploring network structure, dynamics, and function using NetworkX. In G. Varoquaux, T. Vaught, & J. Millman (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 7th python in science conference* (pp. 11–15).
- Hillier, B., & Iida, S. (2005). Network and Psychological Effects in Urban Movement. In A. G. Cohn & D. M. Mark (Eds.), *Spatial Information Theory* (pp. 475–490). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/11556114_30
- Loidl, M., Wallentin, G., Cyganski, R., Graser, A., Scholz, J., & Haslauer, E. (2016). GIS and Transport Modeling—Strengthening the Spatial Perspective. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 5(6), Article 6. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi5060084>
- Lovelace, R., Talbot, J., Morgan, M., & Lucas-Smith, M. (2020). Methods to Prioritise Pop-up Active Transport Infrastructure. *Findings*, 13421. <https://doi.org/10.32866/001c.13421>
- Lowry, M. B., Furth, P., & Hadden-Loh, T. (2016). Prioritizing new bicycle facilities to improve low-stress network connectivity. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 86, 124–140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2016.02.003>
- Łukawska, M. (2024). Quantitative modelling of cyclists’ route choice behaviour on utilitarian trips based on GPS data: Associated factors and behavioural implications. *Transport Reviews*, 44(5), 1045–1076. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2024.2355468>
- Mahfouz, H., Lovelace, R., & Arcaute, E. (2023). A road segment prioritization approach for cycling infrastructure. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 113, 103715. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2023.103715>
- Moran, S. K., Tsay, W., Lawrence, S., & Krykewycz, G. R. (2018). Lowering Bicycle Stress One Link at a Time: Where Should We Invest in Infrastructure? *Transportation Research Record*, 2672(36), 33–41. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0361198118783109>
- Natera Orozco, L. G., Battiston, F., Iñiguez, G., & Szell, M. (2020). Data-driven strategies for optimal bicycle network growth. *Royal Society Open Science*, 7(12), 201130. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.201130>
- Olmos, L. E., Tadeo, M. S., Vlachogiannis, D., Alhasoun, F., Espinet Alegre, X., Ochoa, C., Targa, F., & González, M. C. (2020). A data science framework for planning the growth of bicycle infrastructures. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 115, 102640. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2020.102640>
- Paulsen, M., & Rich, J. (2023). Societally optimal expansion of bicycle networks. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 174, 102778. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trb.2023.06.002>
- Schön, P., Heinen, E., & Manum, B. (2024). A scoping review on cycling network connectivity and its effects on cycling. *Transport Reviews*, 0(0), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2024.2337880>
- Steinacker, C., Storch, D.-M., Timme, M., & Schröder, M. (2022). Demand-driven design of bicycle infrastructure networks for improved urban bikeability. *Nature Computational Science*, 2(10), Article

10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43588-022-00318-w>

Szell, M., Mimar, S., Perlman, T., Ghoshal, G., & Sinatra, R. (2022). Growing urban bicycle networks. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-10783-y>

Turner, A. (2007). From Axial to Road-Centre Lines: A New Representation for Space Syntax and a New Model of Route Choice for Transport Network Analysis. *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design*, 34(3), 539–555. <https://doi.org/10.1068/b32067>

Vybornova, A., Cunha, T., Gühnemann, A., & Szell, M. (2023). Automated Detection of Missing Links in Bicycle Networks. *Geographical Analysis*, 55(2), 239–267. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gean.12324>

Werner, C., & Loidl, M. (2023a). Betweenness Centrality in Spatial Networks: A Spatially Normalised Approach. In R. Beecham, J. A. Long, D. Smith, Q. Zhao, & S. Wise (Eds.), *12th International Conference on Geographic Information Science (GIScience 2023)* (Vol. 277, p. 83:1-83:6). Schloss Dagstuhl – Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik. <https://doi.org/10.4230/LIPIcs.GIScience.2023.83>

Werner, C., & Loidl, M. (2023b). *Supplementary materials to: Betweenness Centrality in Spatial Networks: A Spatially Normalised Approach*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8125632>

Werner, C., van der Meer, L., Kaziyeva, D., Stutz, P., Wendel, R., & Loidl, M. (2024). Bikeability of road segments: An open, adjustable and extendible model. *Journal of Cycling and Micromobility Research*, 2, 100040. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcmmr.2024.100040>

Werner, C., Wendel, R., Kaziyeva, D., Stutz, P., van der Meer, L., Effertz, L., Zagel, B., & Loidl, M. (2024a). NetAScore: An open and extendible software for segment-scale bikeability and walkability. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 23998083241293177. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23998083241293177>

Werner, C., Wendel, R., Kaziyeva, D., Stutz, P., van der Meer, L., Effertz, L., Zagel, B., & Loidl, M. (2024b). *NetAScore* (Version v1.1.1) [Computer software]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11405804>

Wu, X., Cao, W., Wang, J., Zhang, Y., Yang, W., & Liu, Y. (2022). A spatial interaction incorporated betweenness centrality measure. *PLOS ONE*, 17(5), e0268203. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0268203>

Yamaoka, K., Kumakoshi, Y., & Yoshimura, Y. (2021). Local Betweenness Centrality Analysis of 30 European Cities. In S. C. M. Geertman, C. Pettit, R. Goodspeed, & A. Staffans (Eds.), *Urban Informatics and Future Cities* (pp. 527–547). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-76059-5_26

Zhao, Q., & Manaugh, K. (2023). Introducing a Framework for Cycling Investment Prioritization. *Transportation Research Record*, 2677(7), 265–277. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03611981231152241>

Zhao, X., & Guo, Y. (2024). Planning bikeway network for urban commute based on mobile phone data: A case study of Beijing. *Travel Behaviour and Society*, 34, 100672. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tbs.2023.100672>

Zuo, T., & Wei, H. (2019). Bikeway prioritization to increase bicycle network connectivity and bicycle-transit connection: A multi-criteria decision analysis approach. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 129, 52–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2019.08.003>

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Appendix A: Priority score variants

Figure A.1: Priority Score variants for the Vienna case

Figure A.2: Priority Score variants for the ZS case

Appendix B: Network simplification

Figure B.1: Change introduced through network simplification approach for IB, Wien, and ZS

Appendix C: Centrality variants

Explanations: *EBC*: standard edge betweenness centrality (using random node sample; $n=5000$); *Node-filtered*: only including routes between nodes with non-zero spatial weight; *SP*: shortest path; *BP*: bikeable path; *Population-w. BC*: Population-weighted betweenness centrality

Figure C.1: Centrality variants for the ZW case

Figure C.2: Centrality variants for the IB case

Figure C.3: Centrality variants for the Graz case

Figure C.4: Centrality variants for the ZS case

Figure C.5: Centrality variants for the Wien case

Figure C.6: Centrality variants for the NO case

Appendix D: Node subsampling

Figure D.1: Changes introduced by node subsampling for the IB case

Figure D.2: Changes introduced by node subsampling for the NO case